

Modeling Tumor Growth Using Calculus

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1 Table of Contents

- Introduction 2
- Mathematical Model 3
- Assumptions 4
- Calculus Application 5
- Interpretation/Results 6
- Conclusion 7
- Graph 8
- References 9

2 Introduction

I have chosen to research how tumors grow in the human body using derivatives to model that growth. A tumor is an abnormal mass of tissue that forms when cells grow and divide more than they should or don't die when they should. Understanding how quickly a tumor grows can help doctors make better treatment decisions and predict how the disease might progress before it reaches dangerous sizes.

Calculus is very useful for studying tumor growth because it allows us to look at more than just the size of the tumor. The derivative of tumor size over time shows how quickly the tumor changes at any moment. This can give doctors insight into how rapidly it is changing and how aggressive the tumor's behavior is from patient to patient.

For this project, I will use the Exponential Growth Model to show how tumors grow in the human body over time. By finding the derivative of the growth function, I can determine how the tumor's growth rate changes at each point in its development. A high growth rate indicates rapid expansion, while a slow rate indicates that growth is reaching its natural limits. In general, this project shows how calculus can help us understand tumor growth and its importance for treatment.

3 Mathematical Model

I am using the Exponential Growth Model because tumor size changes over time. Tumor cells continuously divide, so the size does not stay constant. To describe this change, the function $T(t)$ is used to represent the tumor size at time t . In the early stages of tumor growth, they are modeled using the exponential growth model because the rate at which the tumor grows is proportional to its current size (also called differential equation). Its mathematically written as:

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = kT(t)$$

This equation shows that the tumor initially grows faster as it gets larger. Early on, its growth is proportional to its size. But factors like limited nutrients, oxygen, and space slow it down over time, so the exponential growth model is most accurate only in the early stages of tumor development.

3.1 Variables

- $\frac{dT}{dt}$: the derivative that tells how fast the tumor is growing at a specific moment. For example, if $\frac{dT}{dt} = 0.0825 \text{ cm}^3/\text{day}$ at $t = 10$, the tumor is growing by 0.0825 cm^3 per day after 10 days.
- k : growth rate constant. Bigger k means faster growth, smaller k means slower growth. For example, $k = 0.05$ per day means the tumor grows 5% of its current size each day.
- $T(t)$: tumor size at time t . For example, if $T(5) = 2 \text{ cm}^3$, the tumor is 2 cm^3 after 5 days.
- T_0 : tumor size at $t = 0$. For example, if the tumor is 1 cm^3 when first detected, then $T_0 = 1 \text{ cm}^3$.

Note: We use cm^3 because the tumor is three-dimensional.

4 Assumptions

An assumption is something people accept as true even if they haven't checked it. It helps make a problem easier to understand because real-life situations are often too complex.

1. The model assumes the tumor grows like a smooth line that keeps getting bigger every moment. But in reality, that's not possible. Tumor cells divide little by little, one at a time, so the tumor basically grows in small steps, not all at once like a straight line.

2. The model assumes the tumor grows faster as it gets bigger like a small tumor grows slowly, but a big one grows quickly because it has more cells dividing. But in reality, that's not true. Tumor growth isn't perfectly proportional to its size because factors like limited nutrients or medicine can slow it down.

3. The model assumes the growth rate constant k stays the same all the time. But in reality, the growth rate changes because as discussed earlier things like limited resources or external factors can make it slower or faster.

4. The model completely ignores external factors like the body's immune system, medicine, surgery, or infections. It only focuses on how the tumor would grow on its own because it is an idealized model for learning purposes.

5. The model works best when the tumor is small and just starting to grow because there's plenty of nutrients and space. But as the tumor grows larger, real growth slows down due to the resources becoming limited, so the exponential model no longer matches reality.

5 Calculus Application

As I stated earlier, the differential equation shows how the tumor size changes over time. By solving it, we get a formula that tells us the tumor's size at any moment. This is useful because if the tumor's current size is known then it can be used to estimate how big it will get in the future.

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = kT(t)$$

- First, we moved all the terms with T to one side of the equation and all the terms with t to the other side.

$$\frac{1}{T} dT = k dt$$

- Secondly, we took the antiderivative which is the opposite of a derivative that helps find the original function. On the left side, the antiderivative of $\frac{1}{T}$ is the natural logarithm of T. The natural logarithm is a function that helps undo an exponent. On the right side, the antiderivative of k is k times t

$$- \int \frac{1}{T} dT, \rightarrow \ln |T|.$$

$$- \int k dt, \rightarrow kt.$$

We add a constant C to include the starting value of T when $t = 0$

$$\ln |T| = kt + C$$

- Thirdly, we remove the logarithm using an exponential which is the opposite of a logarithm. The equation becomes

$$T = e^{kt+C},$$

and using the rules of exponents we split it into

$$T = e^{kt} \cdot e^C.$$

The e^C part is a constant that doesn't change with time, so we replace it with T_0 , the starting size at $t = 0$.

$$T(t) = T_0 e^{kt}$$

6 Interpretation/Results

- The tumor starts out small and grows really slowly at first, but over time it speeds up so the bigger it gets, the faster it grows. This is dangerous because even a small tumor can get huge pretty quickly.

For example if the tumor starts at $T_0 = 1 \text{ cm}^3$ and grows at a rate of $k = 0.05$ per day:

$$T(10) = 1 \cdot e^{0.05 \cdot 10} \approx 1.65 \text{ cm}^3$$

After 10 days, the tumor is about 1.65 cm^3 .

$$T(30) = 1 \cdot e^{0.05 \cdot 30} \approx 4.48 \text{ cm}^3$$

After 30 days, the tumor is about 4.48 cm^3

- The derivative $\frac{dT}{dt} = kT(t)$ models a tumor that grows at a rate proportional to its size over time in the patient's body, because larger tumors have more cells dividing.

For example, when $t = 10$ days, the tumor size is 1.65 cm^3 . So the growth rate is

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = 0.05 \cdot 1.65 \approx 0.0825 \text{ cm}^3/\text{day}$$

When $t = 30$ days, the tumor size is about 4.48 cm^3 . The growth rate becomes:

$$\frac{dT}{dt} = 0.05 \cdot 4.48 \approx 0.224 \text{ cm}^3/\text{day}$$

- Early detection is important because small tumors grow more slowly and they are easier to treat. If the growth rate $\frac{dT}{dt}$ increases, that means that the tumor is growing quickly and treatment for it is needed.
- The exponential model only works the best for small tumors in the early stage but as they grow larger factors like limited nutrients and treatment will slow its growth, so the model becomes less accurate for larger tumors.
- If $\frac{dT}{dt}$ is high, the tumor is growing fast, so doctors act quickly with stronger treatment. If it's low, they can just keep an eye on it.

7 Conclusion

In conclusion, tumor growth in the human body was modeled using an exponential growth and derivatives. The differential equation $\frac{dT}{dt} = kT(t)$ shows that a tumor's growth rate depends on its current size. Solving this equation gives the solution $T(t) = T_0e^{kt}$ which allows us to estimate both the tumor's size and its rate of growth over time.

The results show that tumors grow slowly when small, but their growth accelerates as they increase in size, which explains why untreated tumors can become dangerous quickly. The derivative also provides a precise way to measure how fast the tumor is growing at any moment. However, this model has limitations, as real tumor growth is affected by factors such as limited nutrients, medical treatment, and the immune system, meaning growth is not perfectly exponential.

In general, this project demonstrates how calculus can be used to model and predict real-world biological processes, showing the importance of mathematical tools in understanding disease progression and supporting early medical intervention.

8 Graph

The red curve shows the tumor size $T(t) = e^{0.05t}$ and the blue curve shows the derivative $\frac{dT}{dt} = 0.05e^{0.05t}$, which represents the growth rate.

Both of the curves have the same shape and do increase over time, but the blue curve is smaller because it is multiplied by 0.05.

As the time increases, both curves become steeper which shows that the tumor grows faster as it gets larger, which lets us know that the growth rate depends on the size of the tumor. This is an accurate graph of exponential growth.

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